

Effect of seed rate and row spacing on the yield and yield components of mustard in Bangladesh

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ABSTRACT

An experiment was conducted at the Agronomy Field Laboratory, in Bangladesh Agricultural University, Mymensingh during the period from November 2003 to March 2004 to study the effect of seed rate and row spacing on the yield and yield components of two varieties of mustard. The treatments included two varieties viz. BARI Sharisha-6 and Sambal, two seed rates viz. 7 and 9 kg seeds/ha, and five-row spacings viz. 10, 15, 20 25 and 30 cm. The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications. It was observed that the variety had a significant influence on all the yield and yield contributing characters except unfilled pods/plants. Higher seed yield was obtained by the variety BARI Sharisha-6. The result showed that seed rate had a significant effect on plant height, no. of filled pods/plant, no. of seeds/pod, 1000-seed weight, seed yield and straw yield. Between the two seed rates 9 kg seeds/ha produced a higher seed yield (1.15t/ha). Yield and all yield contributing characters except harvest index were significantly influenced by row spacing. The highest seed yield (1.429 t/ha) was found in 30 cm row spacing. Among the yield contributing characters only 1000- seed weight was significantly influenced by the interaction of variety and seed rate as well as the interaction of seed rate and row spacing. The interaction of variety and row spacing had a significant influence on unfilled pods/plants, seed yield and straw yield. The highest seed yield (2.01 t/ha) was produced when the seeds of Sambal were sown at 30cm row spacing and the same variety with 10cm row spacing produced the lowest seed yield (0.60 t/ha). The interaction of variety, seed rate and row spacing had no significant influence on yield and yield contributing characteristics of mustard.

Keywords: Seed rate, row spacing, mustard, interaction, yield, Sambal, BARI Sharisha-6

INTRODUCTION

Mustard has been grown for thousands of years as lamp fuel, cooking oil and forage. During World War II, mustard acreage increased dramatically because it was used as a lubricant for steamships. Over time, mustard has become a promising oilseed crop in the world (Weber *et al.*, 1995). It belongs to the genus *Brassica* under the family Cruciferae. There are three edible oil-producing species, namely, *Brassica napus*, *Brassica campestris* and *Brassica juncea*. According to the report of FAO (2001), the annual production of mustard in the world was 40.19 t seeds from an area of 26.8 million hectares. It occupies the third position in terms of production and area after soybean and cotton. In Bangladesh mustard is the most widely grown oilseed crop. Out of the total cropped area of 13.53 million ha, oil crops occupy only 0.561 million ha which is about 4.2% of the total cropped area. Rapeseed/ mustard occupies 60% of the oil-cropped area (Wahab *et al.*, 2002).

Mustard oil has only 6 per cent saturated fat, which is lower than any other vegetable oil. It is also composed of 58 per cent monounsaturated fat, a desirable trait to consumers. The mustard meal is a safe protein source in animal feeds with 32-38 per cent protein (Myers, 1995). So, the prospects for mustard appear to be good. In Bangladesh content, it is a popular edible oil in rural areas and is considered important for improving the taste of several food items. It also serves as an important raw material for industrial use such as in soaps, paints, varnishes, hair oils, lubricants, textile auxiliaries, pharmaceuticals etc. Oil cakes and meals can also be used as animal feeds and manures. The analysis of productivity trend reveals that mustard yield in Bangladesh has increased from 672 kg ha⁻¹ to 757 kg ha⁻¹ for the last decade with an annual growth rate of only 1.26% (Rahman, 2002). This is alarmingly poor compared to that of advanced countries like Algeria, Germany, France, the UK and Poland producing 6667 kg, 3507 kg, 3264 kg, 3076 kg and 2076 kg ha⁻¹, respectively (FAO, 2001). The major reasons for low yield in our country are due to lack of both high-yielding varieties and appropriate technologies.

Yield and its formation process depend on genetic, environmental and agronomic factors as well as the interaction between them (Sidlukas and Bernotas, 2003). Therefore, there is a scope to increase the yield level of mustard by using HYV seed and by adopting proper management practices such as spacing, seed rate, irrigation, fertilizer application and other cultural operations. The optimum seed rate plays an important role in producing higher yields. The establishment of optimum plant density per unit area is a prerequisite for having increased grain yield. The plant density can be adjusted by the use of different seed rates and row spacing. Seed rate thus influences yield and yield contributing characteristics of mustard (Johnson *et al.*, 2001).

Mustard yield can be affected by competitive stress among individual plants. Competition occurs when two or more plants need a particular factor necessary for growth, and when the immediate supply of this factor falls below the combined demands of the plants (Milthorpe and Moorby, 1974). The establishment of an optimum spacing is one of the important factors for securing a good yield of a crop. It is well established that the crop environment about light intensity and concentration of carbon dioxide can play a vital role in the photosynthesis of the plant and thus increase dry matter accumulation and vegetative growth of the plant. Hence, plant density per unit area influences crop yield considerably. Optimum spacing ensures proper growth of both aerial and underground parts of the plant through efficient utilization of solar

radiation, nutrients and land as well as air spaces and water (Ward *et al.*, 1985).

Keeping in view the inter-plant competition for optimum plant nutrients, sunlight, moisture and aeration, it may be required to find out a fair combination of seed rate and row spacing to achieve maximum yield under certain agro-climatic conditions. Hence, the present study was undertaken with two important mustard varieties, BARI sharisha 6 and Shambal together with the following objectives:

- i. To find out the effect of seed rate on the yield and yield components of two varieties of mustard.
- ii. To examine the effect of row spacing on the yield and yield contributing characters of mustard.
- iii. To find out interactions among seed rate, spacing and variety.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

An experiment was conducted at the Agronomy Field Laboratory, Bangladesh Agricultural University, Mymensingh during the period from November 2003 to March 2004 to study the effect of seed rate and row spacing on the yield and yield components of two mustard varieties.

3.1 Experimental site

The experimental land was medium-high in elevation and it belongs to the agroecological region of the Old Brahmaputra Floodplain AEZ-9 (UNDP and FAO, 1988). The experimental area is situated at 27.75°N latitude and 90.50°E longitude with an elevation of 18 m.

3.2 Soil

The soil of the experimental land was loamy in texture with moderately acidic in reaction having a pH of 6.8. The status of phosphorus and cation exchange capacity was medium and that of potassium was low (BARC, 1989).

3.3 Climate

The experimental location experiences a sub-tropical climate. The rainfall is usually heavy during *the kharif* season (April to September) and scanty in *the rabi* season (October to March). Low temperatures and plenty of sunshine generally prevail during *the rabi* season.

The monthly total rainfall, average sunshine hours, temperature and humidity during the period of study have been shown in Appendix 1.

3.4 Experimental materials

Two varieties of mustard namely BARI Sarisha-6 and Sambal were used as planting materials. Seeds of BARI Sarisha-6 and Sambal were collected respectively from Oil Seed Research Centre, Bangladesh Agricultural Research Institute, Gazipur and Genetics and Plant Breeding Field Laboratory, Bangladesh Agricultural University, Mymensingh.

The important characteristics of these varieties are mentioned below:

BARI Sharisha-6: BARI Sharisha-6 is a high-yielding variety of rapeseed. It is also known as Dhali. It is under the yellow sarson group of *B. campestris*. Pods of this variety

are comparatively longer. The plant height of this variety is about 100-125 cm. Seeds are yellow with 44-45% oil. The crop matures within 90-100 days and its yield varies from 1.9-2.1 t ha⁻¹ (BARI, 2000).

Sambal: The seed colour of Sambal is brown. The plant type is tall and bushy. The crop matures within 100-105 ay. The seed contains 36-38% oil.

3.5 Experimental treatment

The experiment consisted of the following treatments:

A. Variety :

- i. BARI Sharisha-6 (V₁)
- ii. Sambal (V₂)

B. Seed rate :

- i. 7 kg ha⁻¹ (S₁)
- ii. 9 kg ha⁻¹ (S₂)

C. Row spacing :

- i. 10 cm (A₁)
- ii. 15 cm (A₂)
- iii. 20 cm (A₃)
- iv. 25 cm (A₄)
- v. 30 cm (A₅)

3.6 Experimental design and layout

The experiment was laid out in a three-factor randomized complete block design with three replications. Each replication was divided into 20 unit plots. The treatments were distributed into these plots randomly. The size of each unit plot was 4m × 2.5 m (10 m²). The distance between two adjacent unit plots and that of replications were 0.5 m and 1.0 m, respectively.

3.7 Land preparation

The land was first opened with the tractor-drawn disc plough. Ploughed soil was then brought into desirable fine tilth by 4 operations of ploughing and harrowing with a country plough and ladder. All weeds, stubbles and residues were eliminated from the soil.

3.8 Fertilizer application

The experimental plots were fertilized with a general dose of 90, 70, 50, 30 and 5 kg ha⁻¹ of N, P₂O₅, K₂O, S and Zn from the source of Urea. Triple Super Phosphate (TSP), Muriate of Potash (MP), Gypsum, and Zinc Oxide, respectively (BARC, 1997). Half of the urea and the full amount of other fertilizers were broadcasted during final land preparation and the rest half of the urea was top-dressed before flowering of each sowing.

3.9 Sowing of seeds

Seeds were sown in line maintaining row spacing as per experimental specification. Sowing was done manually. Seeds were placed 2 cm depth and then rows were covered with loose soil properly.

3.10 Weeding and Thinning

Weeding followed by thinning was done after 12 days of emergence and 20 days after emergence. Thinning was done once in all the unit plots with care to maintain a uniform

plant population in each plot.

3.11 Irrigation

Irrigation was done once after 25 days of sowing i.e. before flowering to maintain adequate moisture in the field.

3.12 General observations

The plots under the experiment were frequently observed to notice any change in plant growth and other characteristics. The plant growth was very luxurious.

3.13 Harvesting and threshing

The crop maturity varied with varieties. At maturity (when about 80% of the pods turned straw colour) the experimental crop was harvested variety-wise. Harvesting was done on 24 February 2004 for Sambal on 03 March 2004 BARI Sharisha 6. The harvested plants were tied into bundles and carried to the threshing floor of the Agronomy Field Laboratory. The crops were sundried by spreading on the threshing floor. The seeds were separated from the pods by beating with bamboo sticks and later were cleaned, well-dried and weighed. The weights of the dry straw were also taken.

3.14 Data collection

Data collection on the following parameters from the experiment procedure for data collection was done.

- i. Plant height (cm)
- ii. Number of branches/plant
- iii. Number of filled pods/plant
- iv. Number of unfilled pods/plant
- v. Length of the pod (cm)
- vi. Number of seeds/pod
- vii. 1000-seed weight (g)
- viii. Seed yield (t/ha)
- ix. Straw yield (t/ha)
- x. Harvest index (%)

3.14.1 Plant height (cm)

The height of ten randomly selected plants was measured from the ground level to the tip of the plant and the mean plant height was recorded in cm.

3.14.2 Number of branches/plant

The number of branches of the ten-sample plants was counted and recorded and the mean value was taken.

3.14.3 Number of filled pods/plant

The number of filled pods of each plant was counted and the mean was found out.

3.14.4 Number of unfilled pods/plant

The number of unfilled pods of each plant was counted and the mean was found out.

3.14.5 Length of pod

The length of the pod was measured from the base of the pod to the tip of the pod.

3.14.6 Number of seeds/pod

The number of seeds was counted by splitting five pods per plant.

3.14.7 1000-seed weight (g)

From the seed stock of each plot, 1000 seeds were randomly collected and weight was taken by an electric balance. The 1000-seed weight was recorded in grams (g).

3.14.8 Seed yield (t/ha)

By threshing the plants of the sample area each plot and the mean weight were taken and then converted to t/ha.

3.14.9 Straw yield (t/ha)

The weight of the plants containing grain was taken by subtracting the seed weight from the total weight, the straw weights were calculated and expressed in t/ha.

3.14.10 Harvest index (%)

The harvest index was calculated on the ratio of seed yield to biological yield (seed yield + straw yield) and expressed in percentage. It was calculated by using the following formula (Donald, 1963).

$$\text{Harvest index (\%)} = \frac{\text{Seed yield}}{\text{Biological yield}}$$

3.15 Statistical analysis

The collected data were analyzed statistically by using the ANOVA technique. Analysis of variance was done with the help of the computer package MSTAT. The mean differences among the treatments were tested with Duncan's Multiple Range Test (Gomez and Gomez, 1984).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The experiment was conducted to study the performance of two mustard varieties as influenced by row spacing and seed rate. A summary of the analysis of the variance of the data in respect of all the parameters studied has been shown in Appendices (II-III). The results obtained in this experiment have been presented and discussed below.

4.1 Plant height

4.1.1 Effect of variety

Plant height was significantly influenced by variety (Table 1). Taller plants (123.37 cm) were found in Sambal than BARI Sharisha-6 (119.03 cm). The significant difference in plant height might be associated with the varietal characteristics or genetic makeup of the two varieties of mustard under study. Ali and Rahman (1986) observed significant variations in plant height in different varieties of mustard and rapeseed.

4.1.2 Effect of seed rate

Plant height was significantly influenced by seed rate (Table 2). Higher plant height (124.80 cm) was produced by the use of 9 kg seeds/ ha and lower plant height (117.60 cm) was produced by 7 kg seeds/ha. In contrast, Miah *et al.* (1987) reported that rapeseed was grown with a 5 kg/ha seed rate, which increased plant height.

4.1.3 Effect of row spacing

Plant height was significantly influenced by different row spacings (Table 4). The highest plant height (125.67 cm) was produced by 30 cm row spacing, and it was

identically followed by 25 cm, 20 cm and 15 cm row spacings. The lowest plant height (113.58 cm) was produced by 10 cm row spacing. This might be due to interplant competition as mentioned by Gupta (1988), who recorded significantly taller plants of mustard with wider spacing.

4.1.4 Interaction effect of variety and seed rate

There was no significant interaction effect between variety and seed rate (Table 3). However, the highest plant height (126.73 cm) was found from the combination of the variety Sambal with a seed rate of 9 kg/ha and the lowest (115.20 cm) was found from BARI- 6 sharisha with a seed rate of 7 kg/ha.

4.1.5 Interaction effect of variety and row spacing

No significant influence due to the interaction of variety and row spacing was detected on plant height (Table 5). However, the highest plant height (128.33 cm) was produced by the combination of the variety Sambal with 30 cm row spacing and the lowest plant height (113.83 cm) was produced by BARI-Sharisha 6 with 10 cm row spacing.

4.1.6 Interaction effect of seed rate and row spacing

The interaction of seed rate and row spacing did not show any significant influence on plant height (Table 6). From the interaction effect of seed rate and row spacing, it was observed that 9 kg seeds/ha in combination with 25 cm spacing produced the tallest plants (129.17 cm). The lowest plant height (111.67 cm) was produced by the interaction 7 kg seed rate with 10 cm row spacing.

4.1.7 Interaction effects of variety, seed rate and row spacing

No significant influence due to the interaction of variety, seed rate and row spacing was detected on plant height (Table 7).

4.2 Number of branches/plant

4.2.1 Effect of variety

The number of branches was significantly influenced by variety (Table 1). A higher number of branches/plant (2.73) was produced by BARI Sharisha-6 and a lower number of branches/plant (1.90) was given by Sambal. Khaleque (1989) observed 3.9 and 3.1 branches/plants in TS-72 and Sonali Sharisha, respectively.

4.2.2 Effect of seed rate

No significant influence due to seed rate on the number of branches/plants was observed (Table 2). Wankhede Salami (1970) investigated that different levels of population density did not have any significant effect on the number of branches /plants.

4.2.3 Effect of row spacing

The number of branches/plants was significantly influenced by different row spacings (Table 4). The highest number of branches/plant (3.83) was produced by the application of 30 cm row spacing and the lowest number of branches/plant (1.33) was produced by 10 cm row spacing. Oad *et al* (2001) conducted a field experiment in Pakistan to determine the effect of row spacing on the growth and yield of rapeseed (*B. napus*). The homogeneous seeds of rape cv. P-53 were sown at 3-row spacing (30, 45 and 60 cm). They observed that branches/plant was affected significantly by row spacing and among them, 60 cm row spacing produced the highest number of branches/plant.

4.2.4 Interaction effect of variety and seed rate

No significant influence due to the interaction of variety and seed rate on the number of branches/plants was detected (Table 3).

4.2.5 Interaction effect of variety and row spacing

The variety and row spacing did not show any significant influence on the number of branches/plants (Table 5).

4.2.6 Interaction effect of seed rate and row spacing

No significant influence due to the interaction of seed rate and row spacing was detected on several branches/plants (Table 6).

4.2.7 Interaction effect of variety, seed rate and row spacing

The interaction of variety, seed rate and row spacing did not show any significant influence on the number of branches/plants (Table 7). The highest number of branches/plant (4.67) was found in the combination of BARI Sharisha-6, 7 kg seeds/ha and 30 cm row spacing, and the lowest number of branches/plant (1.00) was found in the combination of Sambal, 9 kg seeds/ha and 10 cm row spacing.

4.3 Number of filled pods/plant

4.3.1 Effect of variety

The number of filled pods/plants was significantly influenced by variety (Table 1). A higher number of filled pods/plant (125.77) was produced by the variety BARI Sharisha-6 and a lower number of filled pods/plant (119.53) was obtained by the variety Sambal.

4.3.2 Effect of seed rate

Significant influence due to seed rate was detected on the number of filled pods/plant (Table 2). A higher number of filled pods/plant (126.20) was produced by the application of 7 kg seeds/ha and a lower number of filled pods/plant (119.00) was produced by the application of 9 kg seeds/ha. Angadi *et al.* (2003) reported that with the increase in seed rate, the number of filled pods/plants decreased. McVetty *et al.* (1988) reported that seed rate had a negative correlation with the number of filled pods/plants.

4.3.3 Effect of row spacing

Different row spacings significantly influenced the number of filled pods/plants (Table 4). The highest number of filled pods/plant (175.42) was found when seeds are sown in 30 cm row spacing and the lowest number of filled pods/plant (79.00) was found when seeds were sown in 10 cm row spacing. Thomas (1984) found that with the increase in row spacing, the number of filled pods/plants increased.

4.3.4 Interaction effect of variety and seed rate

The interaction effect of variety and seed rate had no significant influence on the number of filled pods/plants (Table 3).

4.3.5 Interaction effect of variety and row spacing

No significant influence due to the interaction effects of variety and row spacing on the number of filled pods/plants was observed (Table 5).

4.3.6 Interaction effect of seed rate and row spacing

There was no significant influence of the interaction of seed rate and row spacing on the

number of filled pods/plants (Table 6).

4.3.7 Interaction effect of variety, seed rate and row spacing

No significant influence due to the interaction of variety, seed rate and row spacing was found on the number of filled pods/plants (Table 7).

4.4 Number of unfilled pods/plant

4.4.1 Effect of variety

The number of unfilled seeds/plants was not significantly influenced by the variety (Table 1). However, the variety Sambal produced a higher number of unfilled pods/plant (5.43) and the variety BARI Sharisha-6 produced a lower number of unfilled pods/plant (5.10).

4.4.2 Effect of seed rate

No significant influence due to seeds rate on the number of unfilled pods/plants was observed (Table 2). Both the seed rates produced the same number of unfilled seeds/plant (5.27). Angadi *et al.* (2003) reported that with the increase in the seed rate of canola, the number of unfilled pods /plants increased. McVetty *et al.* (1988) reported that seed rate had a positive correlation with the number of unfilled pods /plants.

4.4.3 Effect of row spacing

Row spacing significantly influenced the number of unfilled pods/plants (Table 4). Thirty cm row spacing produced the highest number of unfilled pods/plant (6.50) and 15 cm row produced the lowest number of unfilled pods/plant (4.08). Thomas (1984) found that with the increase in row spacing number of unfilled pods/plants decreased.

4.4.4 Interaction effect of variety and seed rate

The interaction of variety and seed rate had no significant influence on the number of unfilled pods/plants (Table 3).

4.4.5 Interaction effect of variety and row spacing

The interaction of variety and row spacing had no significant effect on the number of unfilled pods/plants (Table 5).

4.4.6 Interaction effect of seed rate and row spacing

No significant influence due to the interaction of seed rate and row spacing on the number of unfilled seeds/plants was detected (Table 6).

4.4.7 Interaction effect of variety, seed rate and row spacing

There was no significant influence of the interaction of variety, seed rate and row spacing on the number of unfilled seeds/plants (Table 7)

4.5 Length of pod

4.5.1 Effect of variety

The length of the pod was significantly influenced by variety (Table 1). The variety BARIsharisha-6 produced a longer pod (5.63 cm) and the variety Sambal produced a shorter pod (3.29). Hussain *et al.* (1996) observed the longest pod (8.07 cm) in BLN-900 and the shortest pod length (4.83 cm) in Hyola-401.

4.5.2 Effect of seed rate

No significant influence due to seed rate on the length of the pod was observed (Table 2). Angadi *et al.* (2003) reported that with the decrease in the seed rate of canola, the number of pod lengths increased.

4.5.3 Effect of row spacing

Row spacings significantly influenced the length of the pod (Table 4). The longest pod (4.73 cm) was obtained from 20 cm row spacing and the shortest pod (4.23 cm) was obtained from 10 cm row spacing. However, increased the pod length, which might be due to less competition for high, nutrients space and environment. Singh and Singh (1984) and Shrief *et al.* (1990) reported that lower plant density increased the pod length.

4.5.4 Interaction Effects of Variety and seed rate

The interaction of variety and seed rate had no significant influence on the length of a pod (Table 3).

4.5.5 Interaction effects of variety and row spacing

The interaction of variety and row spacing had no significant influence on the length of the pod (Table 5).

4.5.6 Interaction effects of seed rate and row spacing

The interaction of seed rate and row spacing had no significant influence on the length of the pod (Table 6).

4.5.7 Interaction effects of variety, seed rate and row spacing

The interaction of variety, seed rate and row spacing did not show any significant influence on the length of the pod (Table 7).

4.6 Number of seeds/pod

4.6.1 Effect of variety

The number of seeds/pods was significantly influenced by variety (Table 1). The variety Sambal produced the highest number of seeds/ pod (27.20) and the variety BARI sharisha-6 produced a lower number of seeds/pod (12.80). Das *et al.* (1999) reported that MM 7 (Mutant) produced the highest number of seeds/pod (29.2) followed by MM 20 (Mutant) (28.0) and BINA Sharisha 4 (27.8) at Dinajpur.

4.6.2 Effect of seed rate

The number of seeds/pods differed significantly due to variations in seed rate (Table 2). A higher number of seeds/pod (20.30) was found when the seed rate was 9 kg seeds/ha and a lower number of seeds/pod (19.70) was found when the seed rate was 7 kg seeds/ha. Singh and Singh (1984) reported that the number of seeds/pods increased as the plant density decreased. Angadi *et al.* (2003) reported that with the decrease in the seed rate of canola, the number of seeds/pods increased. McVetty *et al.* (1988) reported that seed rate positive correlation with the number of seeds/pods.

4.6.3 Effect of row spacing

The number of seeds/pods was significantly influenced by different row spacing (Table 4). Thirty cm row spacing produced the highest number of seeds/pod (24.83) and 10 cm row spacing produced the lowest number of seeds/ pod (16.25). Thomas (1984) found

that with the increase in row spacing number of seeds/pods decreased.

4.6.4 Interaction effect of variety and seed rate

The interaction of variety and seed rate had no significant influence on the number of seeds/pods (Table 3).

4.6.5 Interaction effect of variety and row spacing

The number of seeds/pods was not influenced by the interaction of variety and row spacing (Table 5).

4.6.6 Interaction effect of seed rate and row spacing

No significant influence of the interaction of seed rate and row spacing on the number of seeds/ pod was observed (Table 6).

4.6.7 Interaction effect of variety seed rate and row spacing

No significant influence due to the interaction of variety, seed rate and row spacing was detected on the number of seeds/pods (Table 7).

4.7 1000-seed weight

4.7.1 Effect of variety

1000-seed weight was significantly influenced by variety (Table 1). The variety Sambal produced a heavier 1000-seed weight (1.97g) and the variety BARI sharisha-6 produced a lighter 1000-seed weight (1.51g). Mondal and Wahab (2001) observed that thousand seed weight was 2.5-2.65 g in Improved Tori-7 (*B. campestris*) and 1.5-7.8 g in Rai-5 (*B. juncea*).

4.7.2 Effect of seed rate

The seed rate significantly influenced 1000-seed weight (Table 2). A higher 1000-seed weight (1.78g) was found when seeds were sown at the rate of 9kg seeds/ha and a lower 1000-seed weight (1.70g) was found when seeds were sown at the rate of 7 kg seeds/ha. Angadi *et al.* (2003) reported that with the decrease in the seed rate of canola, 1000- kernel weight increased.

4.7.3 Effect of row spacing

1000-seed weight was significantly influenced by different row spacing (Table 4). The highest 1000-seed weight was produced (1.84g) and 10 cm row spacing produced the lowest 1000-seed weight (1.64g). Angadi *et al.* (2003) reported that with the increase in row spacing of the canola, 1000- kernel weight increased.

4.7.4 Interaction effect of variety and seed rate

1000-seed weight was significantly influenced by the interaction of variety and seed rate (Table 3). The variety Sambal with 9 kg seeds/ha produced the highest 1000-seed weight (2.04 g) and the variety BARI sharisha-6 with 7 kg seeds/ha produced the lowest 1000-seed weight (1.50 g).

4.7.5 Interaction effect of variety and row spacing

1000-seed weight was not influenced by the interaction of variety and row spacing (Table 5).

4.7.6 Interaction effect of seed rate and row spacing

1000-seed weight was significantly influenced by the interaction of seed rate and row spacing (Table 6). Nine kg seeds/ha with 20cm row spacing produced the highest 1000-seed weight (1.86g) and 7 kg seeds/ha with 10cm row spacing produced the lowest 1000-seed weight (1.53 g).

4.7.7 Interaction effect of variety seed rate and row spacing

1000-seed weight was not significantly influenced by the interaction of variety seed rate (Table 7).

4.8 Seed yield

4.8.1 Effect of variety

Seed yield was significantly influenced by variety (Table 1). The variety BARI Sharisha 6 produced the highest seed yield (1.39 t/ha) and the variety Sambal produced the lowest seed yield (0.85 t/ha). Rahman (2002) observed higher seed yield in BARI Sharisha-7, BARI Sharisha-8 and BARI sharisha-11 (2.00-2.50 t/ha) and the lowest yield in variety Tori-7 (0.95-1.10 t/ha).

4.8.2 Effect of seed rate

Seed rate had a significant influence on seed yield (Table 2). Nine kg seeds/ha produced a higher seed yield (1.15 t/ha) and 7 kg seeds/ha produced a lower seed yield (1.09 t/ha). Angadi *et al.* (2003) reported that reducing the plant population by half from 80 to 40 plants

/m² did not reduce seed yield but seed yield declined as the population dropped below 40 plants/ m². Bryan *et al.* (2001) recommended that a seeding rate between 10 and 15 seeds

/ft² resulted in optimum economic yield. Berglund and McKay (1998) reported that the seeding rate had a significant effect on yield. They also showed a large decrease in yield at 5 seeds /ft² seeding rate and smaller differences between 10, 15 and 20 seeds/ ft². Shastry and Kumar (1981) observed that when the mustard crop was grown at densities of

11.1, 14.8 and 22.2 plants/ m² gave yields in the range of 1.09 to 1.35, 1.39 to 1.41 and 1.34 to 1.35 t/ ha, respectively showing thereby the optimum population to be about 14.8 plants /m². Kondra (1975) showed that narrower row spacing (15 cm apart in a row at 3 kg

/ha), recorded the highest seed yield. From other experiments, he concluded that a rate of 6 kg seed/ ha was optimum for the maximum seed yield of *B. campestris*.

Table 1. Effect of variety on the yield and yield attributes of mustard

	Plant height (cm)	No. of branches/plant	No. of filled pods/plant	Unfilled pods/plant	Length of the pod (cm)	No. of seeds/pod	1000-seed weight (g)	Seed yield (t/ha)	Straw yield (t/ha)	Harvest index (%)
BARI Sharisha-6 (V ₁)	119.033	2.733	125.767	5.100	5.627	12.800	1.507	1.388	3.234	43.142
Sambal (V ₂)	123.367	1.900	119.533	5.433	3.293	27.200	1.973	0.851	2.492	34.284
S ⁻	1.1397	0.1098	1.1248	0.2367	0.0868	0.3628	0.0192	0.0144	0.0356	0.7269
Level of significant	**	**	**	NS	**	**	**	**	**	**

** Significant at 1% level of probability

NS = Not significantly different at P <0.05

Table 2. Effect of seed rate on the yield and yield attributes of mustard

Treatment	Plant height (cm)	No. of branches/plant	No. of filled pods/plant	Unfilled pods/plant	Length of the pod	No. of seeds/pod	1000-seed weight (g)	Seed yield (t/ha)	Straw yield (t/ha)	Harvest index (%)
7 kg (S ₁)	117.600	2.333	126.200	5.267	4.403	19.700	1.703	1.085	2.787	38.569
9 kg (S ₂)	124.800	2.300	119.000	5.267	4.517	20.300	1.776	1.154	2.939	38.857
S ⁻	1.1397	0.1098	1.1248	0.2367	0.0868	0.3628	0.0192	0.0144	0.0356	0.7269
Level of significant	**	NS	**	NS	NS	*	*	**	**	NS

* Significant at a 5% level of probability

** Significantly at 1% level of probability

NS = Not significant different at P <0.05

Table 3. Interaction effect of variety and seed rate on the yield and yield attributes of mustard

Treatment	Plant height (cm)	No. of Branches/plant	No. of filled pods/plant	Unfilled pods/plant	Length of the pod	No. of seeds/ pod	1000- seed weight (g)	Seed yield (t /ha)	Straw yield (t/ ha)	Harvest index (%)
BARI Sharisha-6×7 kg	115.200	2.600	130.667	5.200	5.533	12.267	1.503	1.342	3.128	43.195
BARI Sharisha-6×9 kg	122.867	2.867	120.867	5.000	5.720	13.333	1.511	1.435	3.339	43.089
Sambal × 7 kg	120.000	2.067	121.933	5.333	3.273	27.133	1.904	0.828	2.446	33.942
Sambal × 9 kg	126.733	1.733	117.133	5.533	3.313	27.267	2.041	0.874	2.538	34.625
S ⁻	1.6118	0.4552	1.5907	0.3347	0.1228	0.5130	0.0272	0.0204	0.504	1.0280
Level of significant	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	*	NS	NS	NS

* Significant at a 5% level of probability

NS = Not significantly different at P <0.05

Table 4. Effect of row spacing on the yield and yield attributes of mustard

Treatment	Plant height (cm)	No. of branches/plant	No. of filled pods/plant	Unfilled pods/plant	Length of the pod	No. of seeds/ pod	1000- seed weight (g)	Seed yield (t /ha)	Straw yield (t/ ha)	Harvest index (%)
10 cm	113.583b	1.333	79.000e	4.417cd	4.225	16.250d	1.636b	0.793e	1.967e	39.910
15 cm	121.917a	1.667	96.333d	4.083d	4.475	17.083d	1.652b	0.937d	2.552d	36.518
20 cm	120.083a	2.083	118.038c	5.333bc	4.733	19.417c	1.838a	1.154c	3.041c	37.619
25 cm	124.750a	2.667	144.417b	6.000ab	4.592	22.417b	1.805a	1.285b	3.209b	39.869

30 cm	125.667a	3.833	175.417a	6.500a	4.275	24.833a	1.767a	1.429a	3.546a	39.648
S ⁻	1.8020	0.1735	1.7785	0.3742	0.1373	0.5736	0.0304	0.0228	0.0564	1.1494
Level of significant	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	NS

In a column figures with the same letter or without letters do not differ significantly whereas dissimilar letters differ significantly (as per DMRT) at a 5% level of probability.

** Significant at 1% level of probability

NS = Not significantly different at P <0.05

Table 5. Interaction effect of variety and row spacing on the yield and yield attributes of mustard

Treatment	Plant height (cm)	No. of branches/plant	No. of filled pods/plant	Unfilled pods/plant	Length of the pod	No. of seeds/pod	1000- seed weight (g)	Seed yield (t/ha)	Straw yield (t/ha)	Harvest index (%)
BARI Sharisha-6 × 10cm	113.333	1.500	82.333	4.333	5.200	9.167	1.425	0.987	2.128	46.430
BARI Sharisha-6 × 15cm	119.833	1.833	98.667	4.833	5.633	9.667	1.420	1.142	2.852	40.323
BARI Sharisha-6 × 20cm	116.667	2.500	120.333	5.333	6.017	12.667	1.637	1.395	3.325	42.072
BARI Sharisha-6 × 25cm	122.333	3.167	148.667	5.333	5.867	15.667	1.575	1.625	3.830	42.426
BARI Sharisha-6 × 30cm	123.000	4.667	178.833	5.667	5.417	16.833	1.477	1.793	4.033	44.461
Sambal × 10 cm	113.833	1.167	75.667	4.500	3.250	23.333	1.847	0.600	1.805	33.389
Sambal × 15 cm	124.000	1.500	94.000	3.333	3.317	24.500	1.885	0.732	2.252	32.713
Sambal × 20 cm	123.500	1.667	115.833	5.333	3.450	26.167	2.040	0.913	2.757	33.163
Sambal × 25 cm	127.167	2.167	140.167	6.667	3.317	29.167	2.035	0.945	2.288	37.310
Sambal × 30 cm	128.333	3.000	172.000	7.333	3.133	32.833	2.057	2.005	3.058	34.836
S ⁻	2.5485	0.2454	2.5152	0.5293	0.1942	0.8112	0.2959	0.0323	0.0797	1.6255
Level of significant	NS	NS	NS	*	NS	NS	NS	**	**	NS

* Significant at a 5% level of probability

** Significant at 1% level of probability

NS = Not significantly different at P <0.05

Table 6. Interaction effect of seed rate and row spacing on the yield and yield attributes of mustard

Treatment	Plant height (cm)	No. of branches/plant	No. of filled pods/plant	Unfilled pods/plant	Length of the pod	No. of seeds/pod	1000- seed weight (g)	Seed yield (t /ha)	Straw yield (t/ ha)	Harvest index (%)
7 kg seeds/ha × 10cm	111.667	1.333	80.667	4.667	4.300	16.000	1.530	0.753	1.885	39.594
7 kg seeds/ha × 15cm	121.000	1.667	98.500	4.333	4.550	17.500	1.578	0.890	2.415	36.753
7 kg seeds/ha × 20cm	112.500	2.000	120.167	5.167	4.500	18.500	1.813	1.133	2.938	38.311
7 kg seeds/ha × 25cm	120.333	2.500	151.167	5.167	4.567	22.000	1.832	1.263	3.187	39.285
7 kg seeds/ha × 30cm	122.500	4.167	181.000	7.000	4.100	24.500	1.763	1.385	3.510	38.900
9 kg seeds/ha × 10 cm	115.500	1.333	77.333	4.167	4.150	16.500	1.742	0.833	2.048	40.225
9 kg seeds/ha × 15 cm	122.833	1.667	94.167	3.833	4.400	16.667	1.727	0.983	2.688	36.283
9 kg seeds/ha × 20 cm	127.667	2.167	116.000	5.500	4.967	20.333	1.863	1.175	3.143	36.926
9 kg seeds/ha × 25 cm	129.167	2.833	137.667	6.833	4.617	22.833	1.778	1.307	3.232	40.454
9 kg seeds/ha × 30 cm	128.833	3.500	169.833	6.000	4.450	25.167	1.770	1.473	3.582	40.397
S ₋	2.5485	0.2454	2.5152	0.5293	0.1942	0.8112	0.0430	0.0323	0.0797	1.6255
Level of significant	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	*	NS	NS	NS

* Significant at 5% level of probability

NS = not significant different at P <0.05

Table 7. Interaction effect of variety, seed rate and row spacing on the yield and yield attributes of mustard

Treatment	Plant height (cm)	No. of branches/plant	No. of filled pods/plant	Unfilled pods/plant	Length of the pod	No. of seeds/ pod	1000- seed weight (g)	Seed yield (t /ha)	Straw yield (t/ ha)	Harvest index (%)
V ₁ ×S ₁ ×R ₁	112.333	1.333	81.33	5.000	5.233	9.000	1.310	0.947	2.017	47.054
V ₁ ×S ₁ ×R ₂	118.000	1.667	101.000	5.000	5.667	10.333	1.417	1.063	2.710	39.638
V ₁ ×S ₁ ×R ₃	107.667	2.333	126.000	5.000	5.667	11.000	1.587	1.357	3.157	39.638
V ₁ ×S ₁ ×R ₄	117.333	3.000	159.000	5.000	5.900	15.000	1.663	1.620	3.757	43.113

V ₁ ×S ₁ ×R ₅	120.667	4.667	186.000	6.000	5.200	16.000	1.537	1.723	4.000	43.085
V ₁ ×S ₂ ×R ₁	114.333	1.667	83.333	3.667	5.167	9.333	1.540	1.027	2.240	43.087
V ₁ ×S ₂ ×R ₂	121.667	2.000	96.333	4.667	5.600	9.000	1.423	1.220	2.993	45.807
V ₁ ×S ₂ ×R ₃	125.667	2.667	114.667	5.667	6.367	14.333	1.658	1.433	3.493	41.008
V ₁ ×S ₂ ×R ₄	127.333	3.333	138.333	5.667	5.833	16.333	1.487	1.630	3.903	41.031
V ₁ ×S ₂ ×R ₅	125.333	4.667	171.667	5.333	5.633	17.667	1.417	1.863	4.067	41.761
V ₂ ×S ₁ ×R ₁	111.000	1.333	80.000	4.333	3.367	23.000	1.750	0.560	1.753	45.835
V ₂ ×S ₁ ×R ₂	124.000	1.667	96.000	3.667	3.433	24.667	1.740	0.717	2.120	32.135
V ₂ ×S ₁ ×R ₃	117.333	1.667	114.333	5.333	3.333	26.000	2.040	0.910	2.720	33.869
V ₂ ×S ₁ ×R ₄	123.333	2.000	143.333	5.333	3.233	29.000	2.000	0.907	2.617	33.510
V ₂ ×S ₁ ×R ₅	124.333	3.667	176.000	8.000	3.000	33.000	1.990	1.047	3.020	35.485
V ₂ ×S ₂ ×R ₁	116.667	1.000	71.333	4.667	3.133	23.667	1.943	0.640	1.857	34.713
V ₂ ×S ₂ ×R ₂	124.000	1.333	92.000	3.000	3.200	24.333	2.030	0.747	2.383	34.643
V ₂ ×S ₂ ×R ₃	129.667	1.667	117.333	5.333	3.567	26.333	2.040	0.917	2.793	31.559
V ₂ ×S ₂ ×R ₄	131.000	2.333	137.000	8.000	3.400	29.333	2.070	0.983	2.560	32.821
V ₂ ×S ₂ ×R ₅	132.333	2.333	168.000	6.667	3.260	32.667	2.123	1.083	3.097	39.146
S ⁻	3.6041	0.3471	3.5570	0.7485	0.2746	1.1472NS	0.0609	0.0457	0.1127	34.959
Level or significant	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS2.2988

NS = Not significantly different at P < 0.05

Fig. 1. Effect of row spacing on the yield of mustard

4.8.3 Effect of row spacing

Seed yield was significantly influenced by row spacing (Table 4). The highest seed yield (1.43 t/ha) was produced when the seeds were sown in 30 cm row spacing and the lowest seed yield (0.79 t/ha) was produced when the seeds were sown in 10 cm row spacing. Shahidulla *et al.* (1997) conducted a field experiment during 1994-95 to observe the effect of row spacing and plant spacing on mustard (*B. campestris*). The treatments were three-row spacing (20,30 and 40 cm) and four plant spacing (10, 15, 20 and 30cm). They reported that 30 cm row spacing gave the highest seed yield.

4.4.8 Interaction Effects of Variety and seed rate

There was no significant influence on the interaction of variety and seed rate (Table 3).

4.8.5 Interaction effects of variety and row spacing

Seed yield was significantly influenced by the interaction of variety and row spacing (Table 5). The highest seed yield (2.01 t/ha) was produced when the seeds of Sambal were sown in 30cm row spacing and the same variety with 10 cm row spacing produced the lowest seed yield (0.60 t/ha).

4.8.6 Interaction effects of seed rate and row spacing

There was no significant influence of the interaction of seed rate and row spacing on seed yield (Table 6).

4.8.7 Interaction effects of variety, seed rate and row spacing

No significant influence due to the interaction of variety, seed rate and row spacing was found on seed yield (Table 7).

4.9 Straw yield

4.9.1 Effect of variety

The variety had a significant influence on straw yield (Table 1). A higher straw yield (3.23 t/ha) was produced by the variety BARI Sharisha-6 and a lower straw yield (2.49 t/ha) was produced by the variety Sambal.

4.9.2 Effect of seed rate

Seed rate significantly influenced straw yield (Table 2). The seed rate of 9 kg seeds/ha produced a higher straw yield (2.94 t/ha) and the seed rate of 7kg seeds/ha produced a lower straw yield (2.79 t/ha). Bryan *et al.* (2001) found that the seed rate of 5-8 pounds/ acre produced the highest amount straw of canola. Singh and Singh (1984) observed that when the population density (PD) of 33.3 plants m⁻² was maintained, it gave a higher straw yield of *B. campestris* var. Toria.

4.9.3 Effect of row spacing

Row spacing had a significant influence on straw yield (Table 4). Increasing row spacing increased straw yield. The highest straw yield (3.55 t/ha) was produced when 30cm row spacing was applied and the lowest straw yield (1.97 t/ha) was produced when 10cm row spacing was applied. Gateway Research Organization (2004) reported that canola gave the highest straw yield maintaining 15-inch row spacing.

4.9.4 Interaction effect of variety and seed rate

The interaction of variety and seed rate did not influence straw yield (Table 3).

4.9.5 Interaction effect of variety and row spacing

The straw yield was significantly influenced by the interaction of variety and row spacing (Table 5). The variety BARI Sharisha-6 with 30 cm row spacing produced the highest straw yield (4.03 t/ha) and the variety Sambal with 10cm row spacing produced the lowest straw yield (1.81 t/ha).

4.9.6 Interaction effect of seed rate and row spacing

No significant influence due to the interaction of seed rate and row spacing on straw yield was detected (Table 6).

4.9.7 Interaction effect of variety, seed rate and row spacing

There was no significant influence of the interaction of variety, seed rate and row spacing on straw yield (Table 7).

4.10 Harvest Index

4.10.1 Effect of variety

The Harvest index was significantly influenced by variety (Table 1). The variety BARI Sharisha-6 produced a higher harvest index (43.14%) and the variety Sambal produced a lower harvest index (34.28%). Mehrotra *et al.* (1976) recorded harvest index values ranging from 25 to 40 % in *B. Juncea* that for *B. campestris* from 27 to 42 %.

4.10.2 Effect of seed rate

There was no significant influence on the harvest index by seed rate (Table 2). Scarisbrick *et al.* (1982) used variable seed rates for raising rapeseed and noticed that the harvest index did not increase when the seed rate was raised from 4.5 to 18.0 kg /ha.

4.10.3 Effect of row spacing

There was no significant influence on the harvest index by row spacing (Table 4). Gateway Research organization (2004) reported that a 4 to 6 lbs/ac seeding rate maintaining 15-inch row spacing produced the highest harvest index.

4.10.4 Interaction effect of variety and seed rate

No significant influence of the interaction of variety and seed rate on harvest index was detected (Table 3).

4.10.5 Interaction effect of variety and row spacing

No influence of the interaction of variety and row spacing on harvest was detected (Table 5).

4.10.6 Interaction effect of seed rate and row spacing

There was no significant influence on harvest index by the interaction of seed rate and row spacing was observed (Table 6).

4.10.7 Interaction effects of variety, seed rate and row spacing

No significant influence of the interaction of variety, seed rate and row spacing was detected (Table 7).

SUMMARY

The experiment was conducted at the Agronomy Field Laboratory, BAU, Mymensingh during the Rabi season of 2003-2004 to see the effect of seed rate and row spacing on the yield and yield components of two varieties of mustard. The trial was laid out with two seed rates viz. 7 g and 9kg/ha and five-row spacings viz, 10, 15, 20, 25 and 30 cm in a randomized complete block design with three replications. The size of each unit plot was 4.0 m × 2.5 m. The soil of the experimental plot was loamy in texture with moderately acidic in reaction having a pH of 6.8.

The experimental plots were fertilized with a general dose of 90, 70, 50, 30 and 5 kg/ha of N, P₂O₅, K₂O, S and Zn from the source of urea, triple super phosphate (TSP), muriate of potash (MP), gypsum, zinc oxide, respectively. Seeds were sown in line maintaining row spacing as per experimental specification. Weeding was done twice and irrigation was done once. The crop was harvested on 24 February and 03 March 2004 for BARI Sharisha 6 and Shambal, respectively.

Plant height, number of branches/plant and length of pods were counted before harvesting. Grain yield and yield contributing characters of two mustard varieties were recorded after harvest. The data were analyzed statistically following the ANOVA technique and means were separated by using Duncan's Multiple Range Test (DMRT).

The result of the experiment showed that seed rate had a significant effect on plant height, no. of filled pods/plant, no. of seeds/pod, 1000-seed weight, seed yield and straw yield. The seed rate of 7 kg/ha produced 117.60 cm plant height which increased up to 124.80 cm when 9 kg/ha seeds were used. On the other hand, the increase in seeding rate from 7 to 9 kg/ha significantly decreased the no. of filled pods/plants.

Between the two seed rates, 9 kg seeds/ha produced higher seed yield (1.15 t/ha) and yield contributing parameters like no. of seeds/pod, and 1000-seed weight. Straw yield was

significantly influenced by seed rate and 9 kg seeds/ha produced a higher straw yield (2.94 t/ha).

Results of the experiment showed that row spacing had a significant effect on plant height, no. of branches/plant, no. of filled pods/plant, unfilled pods/plant, length of the pod, no. of seeds/pod, 1000 seed weight, seed yield and straw yield. The highest plant height (125.67 cm), no. of branches/plant (3.83 cm), no. of filled pods/plant (175.42), unfilled pods/plant (6.50), no. of seeds/pod (24.83) seed yield (1.43 t/ha) and straw yield (3.55 t/ha) were obtained by the widest row spacing (30 cm). On the other hand, the lowest plant height (113.58 cm), no. of branches/plant (1.33), no. of filled pods/plant (79.00), length of pod (4.23 cm), no. of seeds/pod (16.25), 1000-seed weight (1.64 g), seed yield (0.79 t/ha) and straw yield (1.97 t/ha) were obtained from narrowest row spacing (10 cm). The highest length of the pod (4.73 cm) and 1000-seed weight (1.84 t/ha) was produced by 20 cm row spacing. The lowest unfilled pods/plant (4.08) was produced by 15 cm row spacing. Row spacing had no significant influence on the harvest index, although the 10 cm row spacing produced the highest harvest index (39.91).

The result of the experiment showed that two varieties had a significant effect on plant height, no. of branches/plant, no. of filled pods/plant, length of the pod, no. of seeds/pod, 1000- seed weight, seed yield, straw yield and harvest index. Higher plant height (123.37), unfilled pods/plant (5.43), no. of seeds/pod (27.20) and 1000 seed weight (1.97) were obtained by the variety Sambal. On the other hand, higher no. of filled pods/plant (125.77), length of the pod (5.63 cm), seed yield (1.39 t/ha), straw yield (3.23 t/ha) and harvest index (43.14%) were obtained by the variety BARI Sharisha-6.

The interaction of variety and seed rate had a significant influence only on 1000-seed weight. The highest 1000-seed weight (2.04 g) was produced by the combination of a variety of Sambal and 9 kg seeds/ha. The seed yield and other yield-contributing characters were not influenced by the interaction of variety and seed rate. The interaction of variety and row spacing had a significant influence on unfilled pods/plants, seed yield and straw yield. The highest unfilled pods /plant (7.33) and seed yield (2.01 t/ha) were produced by the interaction of the variety Sambal and 30 cm row spacing. The variety BARI Sharisha-6 produced the highest straw yield (4.03 t/ha) when seeds were sown in 30 cm rows. Other yield-contributing characters were not significantly influenced by the interaction of variety and row spacing.

The interaction of seed rate and row spacing had significant only for 1000-seed weight. The highest 1000-seed weight (1.86 g) was produced by the combination of 9 kg seeds/ ha and 20 cm row spacing. Other parameters were not influenced by the interaction of seed rate and row spacing. The interaction of variety, seed rate and row spacing had no significant influence on yield and yield contributing characteristics of mustard.

It could be concluded that a higher seed yield of mustard could be obtained by using BARI Sharisa with 9 kg seeds/ha sowing at 30 cm row spacing under the agroclimatic conditions of Mymensingh (AEZ 9).

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